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Determination of Market Efficiency, Volatility and Asymmetric Effect Using Time Series Models at Nairobi Stock Market

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ABSTRACT

Stock market efficiency is an important concept, especially in a growing economy like the Kenyan one. This study empirically determines the form of market efficiency, time-varying volatility effect, and asymmetric or leverage effect of the Nairobi Stock Exchange (NSE) market. Secondary data at the daily NSE 20-share index for the period spanning from January 2001 to December 2010 was used. The market efficiency was determined basing on unit root tests, ADF test, PP test and the non-parametric Runs test. The results indicated that stock returns follow an ARMA (2,1) stochastic process with significant positive serial correlation. The ADF test and PP test clearly gave evidence that the NSE index were non-stationary (random) at level and stationary (non-random) for the first and second differences. This implies that the NSE market is informationally efficient at the weak-form level. Using the non-parametric run test, results clearly displayed NSE market is weak-form efficient. EGARCH and TGARCH model with student's t-distribution were the best models to capture asymmetric effect of stock returns. Since (γ_1) was positive, it indicated significance evidence for asymmetry in stock returns thus presence of leverage effect (good news had a higher impact on volatility than bad news).

JEL Classification: C22, D82, G14

Keywords

Market efficiency, Leverage effect, Volatility, Nairobi Stock Market-Kenya, Stock returns.

1. Introduction

Efficient markets are a necessary prerequisite if it is desired that funds should be allocated to the highest-valued projects thus tax increase to benefit the government. A stock market is termed to be efficient if it fully reflects all information in the market. Market efficiency however is important to the economy since it results to low transaction costs, thus enhancing trading of securities. It also leads to allocation efficiency and enough securities to efficiently allocate risk. Market efficiency and risk-return behavior in a number of emerging stock market economies have been examined by [Bekaert and Harvey, 1997](#); [Bekaert, 1995](#); [Choudhury, 1996](#); [Kim and Singal, \(1999\)](#). An efficient financial market is one in which prices always fully reflect available information. Market efficiency is categorized into three forms as weak, semi-strong and strong ([Fama, 1970, 1991](#)). These forms differ in terms of the types of information, which are used in developing trading strategies. The three forms of market efficiency can be distinguished in the following ways: weak-form efficiency where the prices of financial assets reflect all information contained in the past prices. Semi-strong-form efficiency postulates that prices reflect all the publicly available information. Strong-form efficiency posits that prices of financial assets reflect, in addition to information on past prices, public available information and private (inside) information. Study by [Muhanji \(2000\)](#) found that NSE had a weak form of efficiency while [Dickson and Muragu \(1994\)](#) found that the Nairobi stock market to be efficient. EGARCH model applied to the Kenyan and Nigerian Stock Market returns by [Ogum et al. \(2005\)](#), found that both the stock markets had a weak form of efficiency.

Volatility is a tendency of the assets prices fluctuating either up or down. Increased volatility is perceived as indicating a rise in financial risk which can adversely affect investor assets and wealth. It is observed that when stock market exhibit increased volatility there is a tendency on part of the investors to lose confidence in the market and they tend to exit the market. Studies carried out in the African stock markets include, [Suliman et al. \(2012\)](#), applied GARCH models to the Sudan (KSE) and Egypt Stock Exchange (CASE) by modeling Stock Market Volatility, the empirical results show that volatility is an explosive process for the KSE index returns while it is quite persistent for the CASE index return series. [Frimpong and Oteng \(2006\)](#) applied GARCH models to the Ghana Stock Exchange, [Brooks et al. \(1997\)](#) examined the effect of political change in the South African Stock market. Volatility and volatility spillovers in emerging markets in Africa were investigated by [Appiah and Pascetto \(1998\)](#). However, Kenya's stock market has been under-researched as far as efficiency, volatility modelling and asymmetric effect using non-linear models is concerned.

Asymmetric effect is the impact of positive shocks (good news) on volatility. The Asymmetric effects introduced by [Black \(1976\)](#) show stock returns are negatively correlated with changes in return volatility (good news has higher impact on volatility than that of bad news). Leverage effect implies that bad news (negative shocks) has much stronger effect on volatility than good news (positive shocks) [Black, \(1976\)](#).

However, if the magnitude of volatility response to bad and good news has the same absolute value of correlation then bad and good news have a symmetric effect on stock volatility. The impact of negative shocks (bad news) and positive shocks (good news) on volatility measured by Engle and Victor (1983), reported an asymmetry in stock market volatility towards positive shocks as compared to negative shocks. The asymmetric effect is shown in the EGARCH model with the parameter estimate (γ) when it is positive and statistically different from zero. If the parameter is negative and statistically insignificant at 5% level of significance it indicates leverage effect. Comparison with the TGARCH model, when (γ) is less than zero indicates the same results as (γ) in the EGARCH model. Applying the asymmetric GARCH models to the KSE and CASE, Suliman *et al.* (2012) found a significant evidence for asymmetry in stock returns in both markets, thus presence of leverage effect in the stock return series.

This study empirically investigated the issue of market efficiency, time-varying risk-return volatility and asymmetric effect using ARCH-type models namely GARCH, TGARCH and EGARCH models for the NSE 20-share index.

2. The Nairobi stock exchange *(a brief description)*

Nairobi Stock Exchange (NSE) is the only Stock Exchange market in Kenya. It began in 1954 as an overseas Stock Exchange. The NSE is part of the African Stock Exchange Association (ASEA) founded early 1990s. It's among the most active capital market in Africa in view of its high returns on investment and a well-developed market structure Ogum *et al.* (2005). The NSE market includes the following sectors: agricultural, commercial and services, financial and investment, industrial and allied. The sectors are controlled and managed by the Capital Market Authority (CMA) established by the Act of the Kenyan parliament to promote, regulate and facilitate the development of an ordinary, fair and efficient Capital Markets in Kenya. The NSE market comprises of two main share index, namely NSE 20 share index and NSE All Share index which are mainly used to measure performance. The stock market plays a major role to promote culture of thrift, or saving through facilitating the mobilization of capital for development. NSE improves efficiency in mobilization of savings as capital is allocated to investments that bring the most value to the economy. It provides enterprises with a non-bank source of financing through the sale of shares to the public. It also provides not only the substitution but also diversification of risk to entrepreneurs as they raise capital through equity.

3. Methodology and data

3.1. Determination of Market Efficiency

Secondary data from NSE 20-Share daily index for the period spanning from 1st January 2001 to 31st December 2010 was used. To test if the time series data is stationary, a unit root Philips-Peron test was utilized. Then, transformation of the time series daily index to daily returns was calculated by taking the first-order log difference.

The log return is defined as;

$$R_t = \log \frac{P_{t+1}}{P_t} = \log p_{t+1} - \log p_t \quad (1)$$

where R_t is the daily return and P_t , P_{t+1} are the daily index of an asset at two successive days, $t+1$ and t . The market efficiency was tested with reference to the unit root tests. First, the unit root tests were conducted to test for non-stationarity in the NSE index series as necessary condition for the form of market efficiency. Unit root tests are commonly used to test the stationary property of a time series data. The unit root test is designed to discover whether the series is difference-stationary (the null hypothesis) or trend-stationary (the alternative hypothesis). A series with unit root is said to be non-stationary indicating nonrandom walk. Augmented Dickey-Fuller tests are the most widely applied tests for unit roots. This unit root test provides evidence on whether the stock prices in NSE stock market follow a random walk. Therefore, it is also a test of the weak-form market efficiency. In this study, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test were employed.

Second, a non-parametric runs test was employed to examine whether successive returns series changes are independent or random. Accordingly, it tested whether returns in NSE market were predictable.

3.1.1 Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test

The augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was used to test the existence of a unit root in the series of price changes in the stock index series. The ADF test assumes that y series follows an AR (p) process and add p lagged difference terms of the dependent variable y to the right side of the regression. ADF test utilized the following equations;

$$\Delta y_t = \beta y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^p \gamma_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \beta y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^p \gamma_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \lambda t + \beta y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^p \gamma_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

where, y_t is the price at time t , γ_j are coefficients to be estimated, p is the number of lagged terms and ε_t is white noise. Equation (2) does not include intercept (drift) and trend terms, equation (3), includes constant term α and equation (4), includes constant term and trend term λt . The null hypothesis was that $\alpha=0$, that is, there was a unit root, the series was non-stationary. The alternative hypothesis was that $\alpha<0$. Failing to reject H_0 implied that the time series has the properties of a random walk.

3.1.2 Phillip-Perron (PP) Test

PP tests are proposed by [Phillips and Perron \(1988\)](#). These tests are similar to ADF tests. The difference between the PP and the ADF tests is in how they deal with serial correlation and heteroskedasticity in the errors. The idea of the Phillips-Perron tests is to run a non-augmented Dickey-Fuller regression, and then to adjust for the bias that might occur due to correlation in the innovation term. Phillips-Perron test is a non-parametric test with the following specifications;

$$y_t = c_0 + \rho y_{t-1} + \dots + \mu_t \quad (5)$$

where, y_t is the natural logarithm of the price index at time t , c is a constant and μ_t is pure white noise error term. The hypotheses Phillips-Perron (PP) test was represented as;

H_0 : there is a unit root in the series

H_1 : there is not any unit root in the series (stationary)

3.1.4 Runs test

The Runs test is a non-parametric test that is designed to examine whether successive price changes are independent. A run can be defined as a sequence of consecutive price changes with the same sign. The non-parametric run test is applicable as a test of randomness for the sequence of returns. Accordingly, it tested whether successive returns in NSE market index are predictable.

Here the hypothesis was presented as;

H_0 : The return series of NSE follow a random walk (it is weak-form efficient) for the period of study.

H_1 : The return series of NSE does not random follow a random walk (it is not weak-form efficient) for the period of study.

To perform this test, the premise that if a series of data is random, the observed number of runs in the series should be close to the expected number of runs was put into consideration. Let, n_a and n_b respectively

represented observations above and below the sample mean, median and mode, and r represents the observed number of runs, with $n=n_a+n_b$.

$$Z(r) = r - \frac{E(r)}{\sigma(r)} \tag{6}$$

The expected number of runs was calculated by the formula;

$$E(r) = n + \frac{2n_a n_b}{n} \tag{7}$$

and the standard error by;

$$\sigma E(r) = \left[\frac{2n_a n_b (2n_a n_b - n)}{n^2 (n-1)} \right]^{1/2} \tag{8}$$

3.2 Determination of Volatility

Appropriate GARCH (p,q) models were fitted to predict the time-varying volatility of daily returns in the NSE 20-share index. To confirm for volatility, first existence of the ARCH process in volatility clustering was tested by the size and significance of $\alpha_i > 0$. Next persistence of shocks to volatility was examined on the sum of parameters of ARMA component $\sigma_i^2, \alpha_i + \beta_j$. Values of the sum lower than unity indicated a tendency for the volatility response to decay over-time. Values of the sum equal or greater than unity implied indefinite or increasing volatility persistence to shocks over-time.

3.3 Estimation of Volatility Clustering

To examine if the daily returns series exhibited volatility clustering, first the correlation in the return series was checked by using autocorrelation function (ACF). If ACF exhibited correlation for the return series, then autocorrelation of the squared return for the NSE 20-share index was checked. Ljung-Box-Pierce Q-test was used to test for volatility clustering by first calculating the first-order autocorrelation coefficient in squared returns and then testing the hypothesis, that all the serial correlations of returns are simultaneously equal to zero.

The Ljung-Box-Pierce (Q) statistics (1978) was defined as;

$$Q = n(n+2) \sum_{k=1}^l \frac{r_k^2}{n-k} \tag{9}$$

where n = sample size, l =the number of autocorrelation lags included in the statistics and r_k^2 was the squared sample autocorrelation at lag k . If the computed Q value exceeded the critical value from the Chi-square table given the level of significance, the null hypothesis that all r_k are zero was rejected. If the null hypothesis was rejected it implied that volatility clustering is present in the return series.

3.4 Estimation of Asymmetric and Leverage effect

Asymmetric and leverage effect is performed by the empirical work of Black (1976), where the rise in volatility was observed as a response to “bad news (negative shocks)” and a fall as a response to “good news (positive shocks)”. The TGARCH and EGARCH models captured the asymmetric or leverage effect. The presence of leverage effect was tested by the hypothesis that $\gamma < 0$ and asymmetric effect by $\gamma \neq 0$. If the magnitude of volatility response to bad and good news has the same absolute value of correlation, then bad and good news had a symmetric effect on stock volatility.

4. Data analysis and results

The analysis was facilitated by use of computer software E-views 6.0 and SPSS16.

Figure 1 represents the time plot for the series. A visual inspection of the time plots clearly shows that the mean and variance are not constant, implying non-stationarity of the data. The series was transformed by taking the first difference of the natural logarithms of the values in the series. The transformation was aimed

at attaining stationarity of the NSE 20-share index with the equation given by $R_t = \log \frac{P_{t+1}}{P_t} = \log p_{t+1} - \log p_t$

where, R_t is the daily return and P_t, P_{t+1} are the daily price of an asset at two successive days, $t+1$ and t . The sequence plot for the returns is presented in Figure 2 which reveals well known characteristic of high frequency data. It is easy to observe successive disturbances, although uncorrelated but they are serially dependent. Thus, suggesting the utilization of a nonlinear model and preferably a non-normal distribution for modelling data.

Figure 1: Time plot for daily NSE 20-share index

Figure 2: Time plot for the Log differenced of NSE 20-share index

a) ARMA Models

Table 1 and 2 shows the empirical fittings of several ARMA (p,q) model to the daily return and the goodness of fit statistics respectively. The returns are calculated as the first-order log difference of NSE 20-share index. The series autocorrelation function (ACF) and partial autocorrelation function (PACF) of Q^2 -statistics clearly showed signs of slow exponential decay after the first lag. The AR (p) parameter ($|\theta| < 1$) in Table 1 and MA (q) parameter ($|\phi| < 1$) indicated stationarity and invertability of NSE stock returns respectively. Basic on the Box-Jenkins selection method, ARMA (p,q) models were assessed using the Log likelihood (LL), Schwarz Bayesian Information Criterion (SBIC) and Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) tests. The models that minimized the SBIC and AIC but maximized the log likelihood were considered to be the best. Results clearly indicated that stock returns followed significant ARMA (2,1) stationary trend process.

Table 1: Summary Results of ARMA (p,q) models

Model	Parameter	Estimates
ARMA(1,1)	C	0.000336 (0.3020)
	θ	0.728066 (0.00)
	ϕ	-0.618735(0.00)
ARMA(1,2)	C	0.000332 (0.2448)
	θ	0.056579 (0.0045)
	ϕ	0.165598 (0.00)
ARMA(2,1)	C	0.000333 (0.2609)
	θ	0.176616 (0.00)
	ϕ	0.053998 (0.0067)
ARMA(2,2)	C	0.000332 (0.2393)
	θ	0.180556 (0.0946)
	ϕ	0.000661 (0.9952)

P-Values are given in brackets

Table 2: The goodness of fit statistics for the ARMA models

Model	Statistics
ARMA (1,1)	LL 7549.717
	SBC -6.057072
	AIC -6.064010
ARMA (1,2)	LL 7662.265
	SBC -6.067023
	AIC -6.073961
ARMA (2,1)	LL 7660.274
	SBC -6.067850
	AIC -6.074791
ARMA (2,2)	LL 7656.661
	SBC -6.064984
	AIC -6.071925

Diagnostic checks are presented in Table 3. For ARMA (2,1), the Q-statistics of standardized residuals is not significant indicating the mean equation is correctly specified and Q-squared statistic was significant at 5% which implies that ARMA does not remove the volatility. The Jarque-Bera test rejected the normality assumption in the residuals, (for normality the Jarque-Bera statistics should not be significant). Positive skewness indicates that the data is skewed to the right and the increased positive kurtosis indicates a “peaked” leptokurtic distribution. The Philips-Peron test is utilized to check for the stationarity of the stock returns, the P-value of the test is below 0.05, which implies that stock returns are now stationary.

Table 3: Diagnostic Tests for Standardized Residuals for ARMA (2,1) model

Statistics	ARMA (2,1)
Skewness	0.391749
Kurtosis	183.2439
JB	3412645 (0.00)
Q(36)	50.079 (0.037)
Q ² (36)	639.24 (0.00)
Phillip-Peron test	-47.47972 (0.0001)

P-Values are given in brackets

JB- Represents Jarque-Bera statistics for normality

Q (36) - Represents Ljung-Box Q statistics for the standardized residuals

Q² (36) - Represents Ljung-Box Q statistics for squared standardized residuals

b) Market Efficiency

The ADF and PP tests were carried on the index, d(index) and d(index,2) using the package Eviews6 to empirically determine the form of market efficiency. The tests were performed in levels, first difference and second difference. The null hypothesis of a unit root is rejected at 5% level of significance.

Table 4 and 5 reports the results of the ADF as well as the PP tests for NSE 20-share index at without intercept and trend, with intercept and with trend and intercept respectively. The results clearly show empirical evidence that the NSE index are non-stationary (random) at level and stationary (non-random) for the first and second differences. This implies that the NSE market is informational efficient at the weak-form level. Therefore, prudent investors realized abnormal returns by using historical sequences of stock prices and other market

generated information. This arise from frictions or thinness in trading process, delay in operations and high transaction cost, limited provision of information of firms' performance to market participants, lack of professional financial analyst and brokerage analysis of the stock market returns for investors.

Table 4: ADF and PP Unit Root Test Results (Without Intercept and Trend)

Type of Test	Index Level	t-statistics	Critical value 1% level	Critical value 5% level	Critical value 10% level
ADF	INDEX	0.643997(0.8552)	-2.565879	-1.940949	-1.616615
ADF	D(INDEX)	-30.22853(0.000)	-2.565880	-1.940949	-1.616615
ADF	D(INDEX,2)	-61.15121(0.0001)	-2.565880	-1.940949	-1.616615
PP	INDEX	0.633734(0.8531)	-2.565879	-1.940949	-1.616615
PP	D(INDEX)	-49.50625(0.0001)	-2.565879	-1.940949	-1.616615
PP	D(INDEX,2)	-169.5439(0.0001)	-2.565880	-1.940949	-1.616615

P-Values are given in brackets

Table 5: ADF and PP Unit Root Test Results (With Intercept)

Type of Test	Index Level	t-statistics	Critical value 1% level	Critical value 5% level	Critical value 10% level
ADF	INDEX	0.943654(0.7746)	-3.432748	-2.862485	-2.567318
ADF	D(INDEX)	-30.24160(0.000)	-3.432750	-2.862486	-2.567319
ADF	D(INDEX,2)	-61.13908(0.0001)	-3.432751	-2.862487	-2.567319
PP	INDEX	-0.949685(0.7726)	-3.432748	-2.862485	-2.567318
PP	D(INDEX)	-49.51923(0.0001)	-3.432749	-2.862486	-2.567319
PP	D(INDEX,2)	-169.5036(0.0001)	-3.432750	-2.862486	-2.567319

P-Values are given in brackets

Using the non-parametric runs test to determine the form of market efficiency, randomness and predictability for the sequence of returns was tested. Table 6 display runs test results taking median as the base respectively. The estimated Z-values are significant at 1% level. SPSS16 software is used to obtain the runs test results below. The resulting negative Z values for NSE index and returns indicated positive serial correlation. The runs test show that the successive returns were not independent at 5% level (critical value of -1.96). This suggests that NSE market is weak-form efficient which is consistent with the findings of Ogum *et al.* (2005).

Table 6: RUNS TEST with Median

	NSE INDEX	DIFF(NSE INDEX,1)	DIFF(NSE INDEX,2)
Test Value ^a	3197.95	0.11	-0.12
Cases < Test Value	1262	1261	1261
Cases >= Test Value	1262	1262	1261
Total Cases	2524	2523	2522
Number of Runs	20	939	1612
Z (r)	-49.493	-12.883	13.942
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000

a) Median

c) Time-varying, persistency and clustering of volatility

The empirical results of volatility and risk-returns are presented in Table 7 and 8 respectively. As the variance is expected to be positive, the regression coefficients (C , α_1 and β_1) in the variance equation are all positive and stationarity of the variance is preserved since the coefficients (α_1 and β_1) are less than one. High values of β_1 (0.563785, 0.676532) and Low values of α_1 (0.343366, 0.268657), showed highly persistent and less

reactive in volatility. In other words, the market took more time to fully digest the price shocks than for other stocks. A large value of the GARCH lag coefficient β_1 indicated that shocks to conditional variance took long time to die out implying that the volatility was persistent. The sum of the parameters α_1 and β_1 was approximately equal to unity indicating that volatility shocks were quite persistent (volatility clustering) a tendency observed in high frequency financial data. The sum of the parameters $\alpha_1 + \beta_1$ being close to unity (0.907151 or 0.945189) also implied shocks at time t persists for many periods in the future and indicated stationarity of the stock returns. Thus, the fitted GARCH-M (1,1) model is the best choice for this data which is consistent with the findings of [Box and Jenkins \(1994\)](#) and [Ogum et al. \(2005\)](#) .

Table 7: The Parametric Estimates for the Mean Equations ARMA (p,q)

Parameter	t-distribution
δ	2.330284(0.3189)
C	8.38E-05(0.6643)
θ	0.228208(0.00)
ϕ	0.291086(0.00)

P-Values are given in brackets

Table 8: The Parameter Estimates for the Variance Equation GARCH-M (1,1)

Parameter	t-distribution
C	1.02E-05(0.00)
α_1	0.343366(0.00)
β_1	0.563785(0.00)

P-Values are given in brackets

GARCH-in-mean (GARCH-M) models for different values of p and q were fitted to the NSE data using student's t-distribution test. None of autocorrelation function (ACF) or the partial autocorrelation function (PACF) of the standardized residuals for the 12 lags was significant. This implied that the mean and the variance equations are correctly specified. Diagnostic checks and goodness of fit statistics indicated that GARCH-M (1,1) model to be the best choice. This is consistent with most empirical studies involving the application of GARCH-M models in financial time series data. The fitted models were adequate since their standardized residuals were not significantly correlated basing on the Ljung-Box Q statistics.

Goodness of fit statistics for specific GARCH-M (p,q) models was tested by the student's t distributions as in Table 9 below. The best distribution choice was determined based on the SBIC, AIC and the Log likelihood test. The models that minimized the SBIC and AIC but maximized the log likelihood were considered to be the best. Results clearly indicated that stock returns followed significant GARCH-M (1,1) model. The model adequacy was checked using the Ljung-Box Q statistics for residuals and squared residuals in which the null hypothesis of significant correlations was rejected implying that the fitted model was adequate. The standardized residuals are leptokurtic and the JB statistic strongly rejected the hypothesis of normal distribution. The Goodness of fit statistics and the Diagnostic tests are presented in Tables 9 and 10 respectively.

Table 9: Goodness of fit statistics for the GARCH-M (1,1) model

	GARCH-M (1,1) t-distribution
LL	8954.945
AIC	-7.097965
SBIC	-7.079457

Table 10: Diagnostic tests on the standardized residuals for the GARCH-M models

Statistics	GARCH-M (1,1) t-distribution
Skewness	-14.02079
Kurtosis	459.7093
JB	21992548 (0.00)
Q (36)	38.851 (0.260)
Q ² (36)	0.1240 (1.000)

P-Values are given in brackets

JB- Represents Jarque-Bera statistics for normality

Q (36) - Represents Ljung-Box Q statistics for the standardized residuals

Q² (36)- Represents Ljung-Box Q statistics for squared standardized residuals

In contrast to the empirical success, GARCH model is unsuitable for modeling the frequently observed asymmetric effect or leverage effect due to the positive and negative shocks. To capture these effects, suitable asymmetric models, the Exponential GARCH (EGARCH) and Threshold GARCH (TGARCH) were fitted.

c) Asymmetric and Leverage effect

The EGARCH model proposed by Nelson (1991) was fitted to capture the asymmetric and leverage effect in the financial market that the main GARCH model was not able to capture. The presence of leverage effect was tested by the hypothesis that, $\gamma < 0$ and evidence of asymmetric effect if $\gamma \neq 0$. The EGARCH-in mean (EGARCH-M) models for different values of p and q were fitted to the NSE data using student's t-distribution test. Tables 11 and 12 presented the mean and variance equations respectively. The autocorrelation function (ACF) for the first 12 lags and the partial autocorrelation function (PACF) for Q-statistic clearly indicated no significance. Statistics indicated that the models that minimized the SBIC and AIC but maximized the log likelihood were considered to be the best. Results clearly indicated that stock returns followed significant EGARCH-M (1,1) model. The risk-return parameter δ was positive and statistically significant in the mean equation which clearly confirmed the hypothesis that volatility is a significant determinant of stock returns. This result is in consistent with the portfolio theory.

In the EGARCH-M (1,1) model, the parameter (γ_1) was positive and statistically different from zero indicating the existence of asymmetric effect in the stock returns. This result are consistent with the earlier findings of Ogum *et al.* (2005) on the Nairobi Stock Exchange who found the asymmetry parameter (γ_1) to be positive when modelling the daily NSE 20-share index using the EGARCH models. Since the asymmetric parameter estimate (γ_1) was positive, it implied presence of leverage effect in the stock return series i.e. good news (positive shocks) had a higher impact on volatility than bad news (negative shocks). This could be due to weak-form efficiency information at the NSE market in that companies tend to spread good news and hide

that of bad news. Another reason could be due to hard economic condition that the Kenyan economy has been facing since post-election violence which had a strong effect on the NSE stock market. The squared error parameter (α_1) is positive and significant indicating the existence of ARCH process in the error term, thus suggests the tendency of the shocks to persist (volatility clustering). The sum of the parameters (α_1) and (β_1) is greater than one a tendency for volatility response to shocks display a long trend, implying time-varying volatility in the NSE index stock returns.

Table 11: The parameter estimates for the mean equations ARMA (p,q)

Parameter	t-distribution
δ	0.821399 (0.800)
C	0.000194 (0.3369)
θ	0.228416 (0.00)
ϕ	0.292916 (0.00)

Table 12: Parameter Estimates for the Variance Equation EGARCH-M(1,1)

Parameter	t-distribution
ω_1	-1.070225 (0.00)
α_1	0.306738 (0.00)
γ_1	0.048137 (0.0073)
β_1	0.912241 (0.00)

P-Values are given in brackets

Diagnostics and goodness of fit statistics for the EGARCH-M (1,1) model are presented in Tables 13 and 14 respectively. The Ljung-Box Q statistic of standardized residuals of order 36, Q (36), and the squared standardized residuals, $Q^2(36)$, fail to reject the null hypothesis of the residuals being uncorrelated indicating that the mean and variance equations are correctly specified thus the fitted model is adequate. The Kurtosis in the EGARCH-M (1,1) model still showed positivity but reduced compared to the GARCH-M (1,1) model, while the negative value of the skewness indicated that the data is skewed to the left. This also meant that the left tail is long relative to the right tail. The JB statistics also strongly rejected the null hypothesis of normality in the standardized residuals.

Table13: Goodness of fit statistics for the EGARCH-M(1,1) model

	EGARCH-M (1,1)
	t-distribution
LL	8943.504
AIC	-7.088064
SBIC	-7.067242

Table 14: Diagnostic tests on the standardized residuals for the EGARCH-M models

EGARCH-M (1,1)	
Statistics	t-distribution
Skewness	-10.17060
Kurtosis	303.1714
JB	9508019(0.000)
Q (36)	42.496 (0.150)
Q ² (36)	0.2039 (1.000)

P-Values are given in the brackets

JB- Represents Jarque-Bera statistics for normality

Q (36) - Represents Ljung-Box Q statistics for the standardized residuals

Q²(36)- Represents Ljung-Box Q statistics for squared standardized residual

The Threshold GARCH (TGARCH) model by [Zakoian \(1994\)](#) was also used to determine the asymmetric and leverage effect. The model is based on the assumption that unexpected (unforeseen) changes in the returns of the index have different effects on the conditional variance of the stock market index returns. Specific TGARCH-M (p,q) models were fitted and diagnosed by using the student's t distributions. None of the ACF and PACF for the Q statistics was significant. The student's t-distribution captured tail properties of the data better. The mean and variance equation results for best model TGARCH-M (1,1) are presented in Tables 15 and 16 respectively. The risk-return parameter δ was positive and significant, which is consistent with the portfolio theory. Existence of ARCH process in the error term and the tendency of the shocks to persist was indicated by the positivity of the parameter (α) in the TGARCH-M (1,1) model. The sum of (α) and (β) parameters (0.891905 or 0.936111) was approximately equal to unity implying time-varying volatility in the NSE index.

Table 15: The parameter estimates for the mean equations ARMA(p,q)

Parameter	t-distribution
δ	2.316989 (0.3241)
C	6.59E-05 (0.7340)
θ	0.228807 (0.00)
ϕ	0.292065 (0.00)

P-Values are given in brackets

Table 16: Parameter Estimates for the Variance Equations TGARCH-M (1,1)

Parameter	t-distribution
C	1.03E-05 (0.00)
α_1	0.328246 (0.00)
γ_1	0.029196 (0.6533)
β_1	0.563659 (0.00)

P-Values are given in brackets

The diagnostics and goodness of fit statistics for the TGARCH-M (1,1) model are presented in Tables 17 and 18 respectively. The skewness in the TGARCH-M (1,1) model still showed negativity but had reduced compared to the previous model EGARCH-M. Unlike the skewness, kurtosis in TGARCH-M (1,1) model increased indicating a sharp peak near the mean rather than a flat top as compared to the previous model. Ljung-Box Q statistics for (36) lags for the standardized residuals and squared standardized residuals were not

significant; this implied that the mean and variance equations are correctly specified thus the fitted model is adequate. The JB statistics also rejected the null hypothesis of normality in the standardized residuals.

Table 17: Goodness of fit statistics for the TGARCH-M (1,1) model

	TGARCH-M (1,1) t-distribution
LL	8955.103
AIC	-7.097266
SBIC	-7.076444

Table 18: Diagnostic tests on the standardized residuals for the TGARCH-M models

Statistics	TGARCH-M (1,1) t-distribution
Skewness	-13.99623
Kurtosis	458.6333
JB	21889139 (0.00)
Q (36)	38.931 (0.257)
Q ² (36)	0.1260 (1.000)

P-Values are given in brackets

JB – Represents Jarque-Bera statistics for normality

Q (36) – Represents Ljung-Box Q statistics for the standardized residuals.

Q²(36) – Represents Ljung-Box Q statistics for the squared standardized residuals

The results of estimation and statistical verification for the GARCH-M (1,1), EGARCH-M (1,1) and TGARCH-M (1,1) are shown in Table 19. The log-likelihood, AIC and SBIC tests were used to select the best model that fits the NSE 20-share index data. The higher the log-likelihood value the better the model was to fit the data, [Tooma \(2005\)](#). According to ([Shamir and Hassan 2005](#); [Tooma 2005](#)), log-likelihood value, AIC and SBIC gives the same indication about what model to prefer. The Student’s t distribution for each model was used.

Table 19: Efficiency comparison between the ARCH-type models

	GARCH-M (1,1)	EGARCH-M(1,1)	TGARCH-M (1,1)
LL	8954.945	8943.504	8955.103
SBIC	-7.079457	-7.067242	-7.076444
AIC	-7.097965	-7.088064	-7.097266
Skewness	-14.02079	-10.17060	-13.99623
Kurtosis	459.7093	303.1714	458.6333

A close comparison of the values in the GARCH models, clearly indicated TGARCH-M (1,1) model to be the preferred model due to its maximum log likelihood value. The TGARCH-M (1,1) model is also justified by its low negative value of the residual skewness and the positive (γ) parameter that captures the asymmetric effect. Thus, the best ARCH-type model that fits NSE stock returns data is TGARCH-M (1,1) model.

5. Conclusion

This study empirically examined the NSE stock return behavior, market efficiency, the time-varying risk-return relationship, the persistence of the stock volatility, leverage or asymmetric effect using data for 10-year period. The NSE stock returns showed negative skewness, excess kurtosis and deviation from normality. The volatility tends to change over-time implies that the NSE market is informational efficient at the weak-form level. Therefore, prudent investors realized abnormal returns by using historical sequences of stock prices and other market generated information.

The risk-return parameter was positive and significant, which was consistent with the portfolio theory. The EGARCH-M model displays a significant evidence for asymmetry in the stock returns in that good news (positive shocks) has a higher impact on stock price than that of bad news (negative shocks). This clearly indicated the presence of leverage in the stock return series at NSE market. The sum of the coefficients on the lagged squared error and the lagged conditional variance was high and close to one or unity for the GARCH-M(1,1), EGARCH-M(1,1) and TGARCH-M(1,1) model suggesting that the stocks on the NSE index in general are characterized by a high degree of persistence in conditional volatility.

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